

Workshop Report

Collaborative management centered on Indigenous Peoples and local communities

This document brings together the debates and reflections of the participants of the workshop "Collaborative management centered on Indigenous Peoples and local communities"

This is the **Report of Project Workshop 3: "Power of Connections: Harvesting Lessons and Strengthening Coalitions for Amazonian Conservation"**

May 2026

Organizers:

Collaborator:

Partner:

Report of the Workshop "**Collaborative Management centered on Indigenous Peoples and local communities,**" held between September 1 and 4, 2025 in Manaus, Brazil.

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1. Pan-Amazonia
2. Co-management
3. Community management
4. Biocultural conservation
5. Local knowledge
6. Collaborative governance

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

AICK	Indigenous Association of the Kaluani Community
AMAN	(Aliansi Masyarakat Adat Nusantara) Indigenous Peoples Alliance of the Archipelago
AMPB	Mesoamerican Alliance of Peoples and Forests
APIB	Articulation of Indigenous Peoples of Brazil
ATIX	Xingu Indigenous Land Association
CADAP	Amazon Council for the Development of Aquaculture and Fisheries in Peru
CEDIA	Center for the Development of the Amazonian Indigenous
CIFOR	International Center for Forestry Research
CIPCA	Center for Research and Promotion of Peasants
COICA	Coordinator of Indigenous Organizations of the Amazon Basin
FOIRN	Federation of Indigenous Organizations of the Río Negro
GATC	Global Alliance of Territorial Communities
ICMBio	Chico Mendes Institute for the Conservation of Biodiversity
ICP	Institute of Peripheral Sciences
ICTIO	Citizen Science Platform for the Amazon
IPLC	Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities
ISA	Socio-Environmental Institute
NGO	Non-governmental organization
PICFA	Inter-institutional Platform of Amazonian Fruits of Bolivia
POC	Power of Connections
REPALEAC	Network of Indigenous and Local Peoples for the Sustainable Management of Forest Ecosystems in Central Africa
SEDEPRO	Service of Amazonian Productive Development of Comprehensive Technical Assistance
TCD	Tropical Conservation and Development Program
TGN	General Treasury of the Nation
UF	University of Florida
WCS	Wildlife Conservation Society
WRCS	Wildlife Rangers Club of Suriname

PRESENTATION

This report is a synthesis of what transpired at the workshop "**Collaborative management centered on Indigenous Peoples and local communities**" held from September 2 to 4, 2025 in Manaus, Brazil.

The workshop was organized within the framework of the project *The Power of Connections: Harvesting Lessons and Strengthening Coalitions for Amazonian Conservation*, an initiative of the Tropical Conservation and Development Program (TCD) of the University of Florida (UF), in partnership with WCS-Ecuador and the Juruá Institute, and with financial support of the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation.

The project is based on the premise that the Amazon, one of the most biodiverse and relevant ecosystems on the planet, is deeply connected to global social, political, and economic systems. Changes in international policies, investment decisions, or consumption patterns in other parts of the world directly affect Amazonian peoples and territories. Therefore, the central proposal of the project is to promote collective learning processes and strengthen coalitions and collaboration networks between Pan-Amazonian countries, connecting academic, ancestral, and local knowledge.

The project recognizes that effective conservation of the Amazon can only be achieved with Amazonians and not in spite of them. Thus, the knowledge, practices, and ways of life developed by Indigenous Peoples, traditional communities and local organizations offer valued innovative and replicable solutions to sustainability challenges.

The project has a duration of 19 months, starting in January 2025 and ending in September 2026. It includes an international conference in Gainesville (USA) with participation of thematic leaders and partner representatives. Throughout this period, five thematic workshops are being held in different countries of the Amazon:

1. Sociobioeconomies and Conservation Finance (Brazil, May 2025)
2. Reshaping institutions for the next generation conservation leaders (Bolivia, July 2025)
3. Collaborative governance centered on Indigenous Peoples and local communities (Brazil, September 2025)
4. Innovations in the research process (Peru, December 2025)
5. Indigenous rights and governance instruments (Ecuador, January 2026).

Expected results include the implementation of a continuous learning model through iterative events that promote in-depth analyses of five critical conservation issues and the promotion of people-centered development mechanisms, which are often invisible in leadership training and the stimulation of intergenerational work.

The workshop reported in this document was the third, focusing on community-centered collaborative management of natural resources and territories. Representatives of civil society organizations, Indigenous groups, community associations, government, researchers, and the private sector participated, composing a plural space for exchange, listening, and collective construction. The general objectives of the meeting were to strengthen ties between collaborative management actors; provide an exchange of tools, approaches, practices, and principles; and outline priority next steps to advance collaborative management practice.

Here we highlight the main activities, moments, and content discussed by the participants and collected by the University of Florida team. We hope that this information can contribute to the strengthening of governance and socio-environmental development processes across the Pan-Amazonian region.

Figure 1. Group of workshop participants

WORKSHOP'S ORGANIZATION

This workshop, like the other four thematic workshops of the POC project, was the result of collaboration between the thematic leaders and the University of Florida (UF) team. The thematic leaders were selected several months in advance for their extensive experience in the Amazon and in the specific theme of the workshop. From then on, through weekly meetings, they and the UF team shaped the event: first by jointly defining the objectives and then by drawing up the list of participants, selected for the relevance of their knowledge and their approach to action.

A few months before the workshop, the facilitation team was also formed, led by two people: the facilitator of the UF team and an external facilitator from an Amazonian country, the latter also identified by the workshop organizing team. With the objectives defined and the participants confirmed, this team designed the agenda, which was subsequently reviewed and validated by the entire organizing group.

During the workshop, facilitation was carried out with a flexible and participatory approach, ensuring that each participant could contribute meaningfully to the discussions. Each day, and even sometimes during the sessions, the organizing team met briefly to reflect, evaluate the development of the process and, if necessary, adjust the agenda along the way.

Finally, after the workshop, the organizing team worked on the results, which were shared with the participants for validation in a virtual meeting. This was an iterative process, which was refined and strengthened with each workshop.

Objectives and agenda of the workshop

This workshop aimed to create a space where key conservation actors from across the Amazon could exchange experiences, strategies, and key lessons on the event's themes.

Specific objectives:

- Build a community among practitioners of collaborative management (or co-management).
- Share lessons learned from innovative co-management initiatives in the Amazon.
- Strengthen connections between community leaders, public agents and researchers, fostering lasting collaborations.
- Exchange practical and effective tools and principles for co-management with Indigenous Peoples and local communities.
- To share successful experiences that can be replicated in other territories and places.
- Define the next priority steps to advance the practice of co-determination.

Table 1. Workshop agenda

Day	Central Theme	Activities
Day 1 01/09/2025	Building community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome and presentation of the objectives, contents and methodology of the workshop • Introducing participants (who I am, where I work)
Day 2 02/09/2025 08h00 – 18h00	Setting the Stage: Territories, Voices, and Realities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The concept of Collaborative Management: <i>What do we mean by Collaborative Management and why is it important?</i> Responses from participants by sector: NGOs, local communities, governments, research institutions • Experiences by Type of Management: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Which actors are involved?</i> - <i>What are the main challenges?</i> - <i>What progress is there?</i> Participants' responses by type of management: territorial, tourism, fauna/hunting, educational management, fishing timber and non-timber resources • Preparation of individual posters and presentation of the first half of them
Day 3 03/09/2025 08h30 – 17h30	Practices in Action: Tools, Good Practices and Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding the challenges • Sharing success stories in collaborative management • Experiences with a gender perspective, inclusion of young people, and equitable benefits • Presentation of the other half of individual posters

<p>Day 4 04/09/2025 08h30 – 17h00</p>	<p>Commitments, Partnerships, and the Road Ahead</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group discussions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>What have we learned about what makes collaboration work?</i> - <i>What should happen for all parties to feel that their needs are being met?</i> - <i>How to strengthen intercultural knowledge that promotes collaborative management?</i> • Looking to the future: <i>How can this group collaborate for the future?</i> • Evaluation of the workshop and farewell
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Workshop participants

The workshop featured a diverse group of 22 guests who live and work on issues related to collaborative management in the Amazon. Participants are part of local communities and Indigenous groups, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), government entities, the private sector, and research institutions. This group was joined by 9 people from the organizing team.

Table 2. List of participants present at the workshop

Name	Institution	Country of operations	Email
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DAY 1: COMMUNITY BUILDING

The opening of the workshop established a common framework that transcended a simple protocol welcome. From the beginning, it was emphasized that the meeting did not seek to produce quick consensus or replicate standardized models, but to create a space for honest exchange on the real conditions in which collaborative management is developed in the Amazon.

The initial interventions underlined that collaborative management implies a profound paradigm shift: Indigenous and local communities should not be understood as beneficiaries of external policies or projects, but as political and technical actors with the capacity to lead territorial processes and produce relevant knowledge. This emphasis placed the workshop in a critical perspective in the face of verticalized conservation approaches and extractive research practices.

Figure 2. Participant during the presentation of their countries of origin and area of operation in the Amazon

Likewise, the Amazon was highlighted as an interdependent socio-ecological system, where decisions made on a global scale have a direct impact on local territories. In this context, the workshop was presented as an effort to connect scales, without diluting territorial specificities or subordinating local knowledge to external frameworks.

1.1. Welcome

The thematic leaders, João Campos – Silva and Galo Zapata – Ríos, welcome workshop participants. Subsequently, they present the objectives, contents, and methodology of the workshop.

João highlighted the diversity of participant countries of origin and the importance of discussing collaborative management. It presents the Juruá Institute's lines of work and contrasts this approach with the traditional approach of biodiversity protectionism. He stressed that the strength of the Amazon is in its collectivity, respect for territorial visions, and connections.

Galo recognized the arduous process that made the workshop possible. He stressed that the participants are key actors with valuable knowledge and that the objective is to collectively build paths for collaborative management, highlighting the importance of joint participation in this process.

João Campos-Silva:

The strength of the Amazon is in the collective. No one does anything alone. Collaborative management is born precisely from this understanding.

1.2. Presentation of the POC project

Professor Karen Kainer, from the University of Florida, presented the project *The Power of Connections*, and its purpose to organize five workshops in different Amazonian countries, this being the third of them. She also shared that this initiative seeks to promote reflection on lessons learned, strengthen ties, and promote collaboration for the lasting biocultural conservation of the Pan-Amazon, consolidating key strategic alliances.

Karen Kainer:

The news talks a lot about the destruction of the Amazon, but it almost never talks about what people do every day to care for and create solutions in the territories. This project seeks to make Amazonian solutions visible and connect them on a larger scale, without losing their territorial roots.

Figure 3. Karen Kainer's Welcome Remarks and Presentation of the POC Project

Galo Zapata-Ríos:

Each person who is here was invited because they have something fundamental to contribute. This space is not for transmission, it is for joint construction.

1.3. Introduction of participants

Using a map of the Amazon biome, each participant indicated their origin and location of where they work (Figure 4). The workshop was attended by representatives from seven Amazonian countries: Bolivia, Brazil, Colombia, Ecuador, Peru, Guyana and Suriname. In addition, participants indicated the sector they represented through colored strips: local communities and Indigenous Peoples (red), government (blue), NGOs (yellow), or research institutions (orange).

Figure 4. Origin and area of activity of the participants in the workshop.

DAY 2: SETTING THE STAGE. TERRITORIES, VOICES, AND REALITIES

2.1. Expectations of the workshop

The sharing of expectations evidenced a diversity of territorial contexts, along with a strong convergence around structural challenges of collaborative management in the Amazon. This moment consolidated the workshop as a community of practice, rather than as an isolated event, and reaffirmed collaborative management as a relational, dynamic, and long-term process.

To begin the workshop, reference was made to the virtual meeting held on August 26, two weeks before the workshop, and some of the expectations shared that day about this face-to-face workshop were presented. Among them:

- Knowledge exchange
- Connect with others working in collaborative management
- Promote a community of practice
- Systematize good practices
- Better understand the context of collaborative management

Tuntiak Patricio Katan Jua:

My expectation is how to maintain this connection afterwards. It is not enough to say that we are going to collaborate. The challenge is to put it into practice.

Rodrigo Marcelino:

Here we all do very similar things, but with different tools. Understanding those differences is what interests me most.

The facilitators opened the space for people who could not attend that virtual meeting, including many representatives of local communities and Indigenous groups, to share their expectations and complement the above. Among the main things, it was mentioned:

- Exchange of tools and methodologies that are really generating change.
- Gain innovative ideas to take back to their communities.
- Discuss strategies on how to use what was learned in this workshop to transmit it to young people in the Amazonian territory.
- Discuss how territorial governance is promoted through collaborative management.
- Discuss how to promote collaborative management in contexts where protected areas overlap with Indigenous territories.
- Think together about how to keep the connections 'alive' between participants after the workshop.

Figure 5. Intervention of participants about their expectations of the workshop

2.2. The concept of Collaborative Management

A group activity was organized to define together what we mean by collaborative management. This activity divided participants into groups **by sector** they represented (community-based associations, governments, NGOs, research institutions) to discuss the following questions:

- *What do we mean by collaborative management?*
- *Why is it important?*

Participants began by presenting their individual definitions, which then fed into the joint construction of a consensual definition. The collective work carried out in each of 4 groups is detailed below.

1) Community-Based Associations Group

Concept: Collaborative management is the form of organization that encompasses (and values) the diversity of knowledge, skills, capacities, and roles for making collective decisions. Collaborative management is not limited to specific projects, but encompasses territorial governance, cultural and environmental protection, and the relationship between communities, grassroots organizations, NGOs, the State, academia, and other external actors. This form of management makes it possible to face complex territorial problems, such as invasions, external pressure and conflicts, from a logic of co-responsibility.

Why is it important?

- It encourages innovation and the development of social skills.
- It allows the strengthening of Indigenous identity in decision-making, putting them as protagonists and at the center of discussions on collaborative management in their territories.
- Local communities are understood as partners and not beneficiaries.
- It strengthens autonomy and respect for the community.
- It protects social biodiversity, ensuring that decisions about the territory are made more fairly with the active participation of the communities that live there.
- It is conducive to the training of new generations of managers.
- It allows respect for local ways of life, as well as cultural and natural values.

- It allows for shared decision-making, where all parties have a voice, as well as the decentralization of power.
- It integrates cultural, linguistic, and worldview diversity.
- It allows us to co-create our own models of development and territorial protection.
- It is understood that each actor has a role, which generates a sense of belonging, empowerment, co-responsibility, and mutual learning.
- It allows us to understand the context of the region and the territory, to seek solutions through collaborations between actors.

Figure 6. Participants during group work

Katan Jua Tuntiak Patrick:

It is not a question of imposing a vision, but of articulating different visions with a common strategy.

Suellen Samanta dos Santos Barreto Baré:

Collaborative management is when everyone has a voice: women, young people, the elderly. This is how we live in our community.

Ruth Marilyn Buchapi Velasco (Marisita):

It is not easy to work where Indigenous territory is also a protected area, but it is possible when co-management involves all actors.

Darío Emilio Casimiro:

Collaborative management strengthens autonomy and allows for fairer decisions.

2) Group of government representatives

Concept: Collaborative management is a collective work oriented towards a common vision of the territory. It implies moving to it to understand its dynamics and ways of thinking. Through dialogue, meeting points are generated that allow new perspectives to be built and shared interests to be recognized. It is an ongoing process that is deeply dependent on the context, so there is no single recipe, and it requires the ability to understand the other's thinking, values, and interests.

Why is it important?

- It recognizes the interconnectedness between people, ecosystems, and spirituality.
- It connects the actors in the territory: local communities, government, academia, NGOs, and the private sector, so that decisions can be made in the territory together.
- It strengthens territorial governance through clear social agreements. Failure to comply with them weakens confidence.
- It is understood that collaborative management varies depending on whether it is in titled communities or recent settlements.
- It recognizes the limitations of the State: hierarchical processes and reduced capacities, and the need for specific efforts at the local level.
- The willingness of the communities to relate to the government stands out, in the face of its lack of openness.

Figure 7. Participant during the presentation of the group work carried out

Jenny Paola Gallo Santos:

There is a romantic vision of the Amazon, but the Amazon has people, with real needs. The communities are ready to dialogue with the government. The problem is that the government is not always ready to dialogue with them.

3) Non-Governmental Organizations - NGOs Group

The group discussed collaborative management as a practical, situated, and relational process, built from the daily experience of the communities and not as a predefined technical model.

Concept: Collaborative management is a process and a space that seeks solutions to collective problems related to territory or natural resources. It stresses the importance of putting people at the center, not resources. It must be aligned with the expectations and aspirations of the communities, articulating the roles according to the possibilities of each actor. It seeks to reduce conflicts, connect different actors, and promote egalitarian alliances. It implies symmetry of power, empathy between actors, and recognition of the different contexts – rural and urban – of the Amazon. It is rights-based and geared towards responding to collective problems. Sometimes, NGOs share values with communities, but their main role is to support and advise.

In this sense, territorial management appears to be linked to the defense of the territory against external pressures, the strengthening of internal organization, and the construction of collective agreements. The limits of collaborative management when it relies excessively on external support for technical and administrative functions were also discussed.

Why is it important?

- It seeks to strengthen Indigenous Peoples and local communities, amplifying their voices and recognizing and valuing their knowledge and practices
- It allows decisions to be made based on the demands associated with the territory.
- It articulates roles, objectives, and actors, each from their skills and levels of action.
- It promotes conflict resolution.
- It involves the strengthening and training of actors.
- It increases the chances of achieving common goals.

Figure 8. Participant during the presentation of the group work carried out

4) Group of researchers

Concept: This group began by discussing the concepts of governance, management and co-management, and came to understand them on three levels. Governance is understood as a broader, legal, and institutional framework that regulates the interaction between different actors. Management is related to operational management, which involves decision-making at various levels. Finally, co-management consists of knowing how to dialogue between these actors to share responsibilities, rights and benefits associated with territories and their resources. Among actors influencing this scenario are NGOs, researchers, and the private sector. In short, the legitimacy of management depends on the degree to which these processes are participatory and collaborative; hence, the need to promote truly collaborative management.

Why is it important?

- The concept of collaborative management allows us to understand the context more broadly and to see beyond the technical or specific aspects, inviting researchers to look at the system as a whole.
- It also invites the integration of different types of knowledge, promoting a dialogue between knowledges.
- The use of this concept by researchers promotes more applied research, with concrete results in the territory and in the resolution of real problems.

Figure 9. Presentation of the group work carried out

Vanessa Rodríguez:

I was struck at first by how different the understanding [of the concept of collaborative management] is for each group. While for community members, collaborative management has to do with an organizational model, for NGOs it has more to do with a process of construction. For academia it has to do with understanding the context, and for the government it has more to do with the space to bring people together and articulate actions. They are four different forms, but they also share some common elements such as the importance of the territorial approach, differences between the actors, the legitimacy of the process.

Table 3. Summary of the understanding of Collaborative Management by sector

Group	How do you define collaborative management?	Why is it important?
1. Community-Based Partnerships	A form of organization that integrates knowledge, and diverse roles for collective decisions that articulate territorial and environmental goals.	It strengthens identity, autonomy, and co-responsibility; promotes innovation, equity, cultural respect, and protection of socio-biodiversity.
2. Government representatives	Collective process to build a common vision of the territory through dialogue and understanding of the other's thinking; it depends on the context.	It strengthens territorial governance, connects diverse actors, recognizes limitations of the State, and values the community's willingness to dialogue.
3. Non-governmental organizations (NGOs)	A process that starts from collective problems of the territory; it centers people rather than resources and seeks equitable alliances with empathy and respect for diverse contexts.	It strengthens local capacities, promotes conflict resolution and shared decisions, articulates roles, and amplifies community voices.
4. Researchers	Framework that integrates governance, management, and co-management to share responsibilities, rights, and benefits among actors.	The use of the concept promotes applied research, dialogue between knowledges, and a comprehensive understanding of the system beyond the technical.

Additional comments:

Tuntiak:

I think that Collaborative Management means breaking traditional systems where it is usually thought that I or my group believes that I am the only one that works or does things well. For me it is a model, an organizational mechanism where the enabling conditions, institutional arrangements, and the construction and execution of actions are prioritized. Knowing that there are various ecosystems: academic, scientific, community, cultural, economic and development - all together working from their particularities, from their own experiences, experiences and knowledge. In that sense, I don't see it as an imposition of a sector, but rather as a collective construction of objectives of actions and results where each one has their role. This allows each sector to have a sense of belonging, and to feel that it is also co-building a solution. In this process, each actor is empowered and feels responsible and co-generates learning.

Dario Baniwa:

What caught my attention the most is the need for intercultural and collaborative research, which is a process of strengthening knowledge based on the knowledge of each social actor. This strengthens governance. But we have a great challenge: sometimes, academic science does not recognize traditional knowledge as science. In management, those who dominate best are the Indigenous Peoples who use indigenous technologies, whose origin is due to their history, to their people.

Reflections from the thematic leaders:

Galo: In defining collaborative management and its importance, each group representing community-based associations, government representatives, NGOs, and researchers shared some differences in their approach: Collaborative management as a process, a system, or an organization, which depends on one's point of view and level of action. However, all groups point to a common objective, the need to assume shared responsibilities to achieve shared benefits.

All groups aim at the recognition of the rights, knowledge, and leadership of local populations as the legitimate users of these resources. There is the challenge of building trust, sharing power, and seeking that symmetry. This is an issue that includes approaches to promote justice, equity, inclusion, and to achieve long-term environmental and social sustainability.

Finally, collaborative management must work within the context of adaptive management. It has to evolve according to the changes that exist and that are constant. So, we have to be open to the fact that these changes are going to be there, and we are going to have to adapt as various actors collaborating together.

João: Collaborative management is a concept that is being transformed according to reality and according to people's perception and understanding. But it comes from the understanding that Indigenous Peoples and local communities are no longer beneficiaries, but protagonists of a process. And that this understanding is increasingly entering other spaces, whether in government, in the third sector, or in academia. This recognition of local peoples as protagonists not only of the actions of the territories, but also protagonists in the generation of knowledge. The concept is understood from a paradigm shift, which leads to a reflection by the actors on what is the protagonism of local action and what is the alliance.

2.3. Experiences by type of management

Collaborative management takes different forms depending on the context. Therefore, to begin the next activity, the facilitators stressed that the diversity of approaches does not represent an obstacle, but an opportunity to better understand the conditions that make collaboration possible or limit it. The activity that follows is an exchange of experiences in Collaborative Management, by type of management. Guiding questions include:

- Which actors are involved?
- What are the main challenges?
- What progress is there?

The participants were divided into six groups, according to the type of management that their organization represents: territorial, tourism, fauna/hunting, educational management, fishing, and timber and non-timber resources.

Among the main lessons presented by the different groups, it is worth highlighting:

- Effective territorial management usually begins with processes of affirmation of rights and recognition of the territory, before moving towards productive or conservation schemes.
- Dependence on intermediaries remains one of the main obstacles to the economic autonomy of communities.
- There are significant gaps between national regulations and territorial realities, especially in Indigenous and rural contexts.
- Pressure from illegal or unregulated external actors (mining, poaching, illegal fishing) can disrupt community conservation efforts.

Figure 10. Group work by type of management

1) Territorial Management Group

- The group discussed various cultural rescue practices in the territories and how they strengthen community identity and management.

- The importance of developing collectively constructed territorial management plans involving all local actors was addressed.
- One of the shared challenges was the overlap between protected natural areas and Indigenous territories, which generates tensions and limitations in governance.
- It was highlighted that there are multiple actors with different decision-making capacities, which requires clear coordination and articulation mechanisms.
- Logistics represent a significant barrier: mobilizing representatives from remote communities involves high costs and complex planning.

João Campos-Silva:

Many times we talk about conservation without considering the real costs that communities assume to protect huge areas.

- The difficulty of organizing inclusive decision-making spaces that integrate the voices and perspectives of all sectors was also mentioned.
- The group reflected on the challenges of facilitating deliberative processes with large numbers of participants. As an example, Tuntiak explained that in the Achuar Nationality of Ecuador, assemblies are organized with representatives of 500 communities, electing 5 delegates for each one to participate in decisions about the territory, with about 3,000 people represented.
- It was noted that, although each country and Indigenous group has its own organizational structures and specific rules for protected areas, common problems were identified: lack of inter-institutional coordination, logistical obstacles, and regulatory overlap.
- The group agreed on the need to strengthen representation, ensure resources for community participation, and design culturally relevant and operationally viable decision-making processes.

2) Tourism Management Group

- An ecotourism experience was described in Madre de Dios (Peru), managed by the Ese Eja native community of the town of Infierno. Their territory encompasses 10,000 hectares, of which 3,000 hectares are destined for ecotourism. They have been dedicated to this activity since 1996, since they began a collaboration with the company Rainforest Expeditions. Now the community has its own venture, called Bawaia Expeditions, 100% operated by the community. It was stressed that conservation guarantees the presence of fauna, key to ecotourism; as well as the importance of tourism-related research and scientific tourism opportunities, including the description of new species of global interest.

3) Wildlife/Game Management Group

- The group, although small and diverse, identified common challenges in wildlife conservation and the management of game species.
- The local perception of species abundance influences management decisions, such as the urgency or not of adopting protection measures. For example, the case of a species that is common in the Wapichana Indigenous territory in Guyana but has disappeared in other countries.

- The health of the ecosystem determines the health of species, so improving territorial management directly benefits the fauna.
- Hunting creates governance challenges, especially when species abundance attracts external actors that put pressure on territories.
- There are regulatory differences between countries that affect territorial formalization and wildlife management, which complicates management in transboundary areas. On the other hand, regulations can be very strict in some Amazonian countries. For example, in Ecuador, where hunting is only allowed by Indigenous People within Indigenous lands.
- The conservation of one umbrella species often favors other species that share habitat and ecological processes, showing the value of integrated management approaches.

4) Educational Management Group

- The group highlighted 3 important experiences: Experience in fire management and fire education, including the challenge of fire in the Xingu Indigenous Territory, which is an Indigenous reserve located in the state of Mato Grosso, Brazil. The challenges of involving Indigenous youth in these educational activities were mentioned, as they have less interest and resources to ensure their participation.
- The second experience was an academic work on methodologies to involve different ethnic groups in urban contexts, with the aim of decolonizing education in the city of Manaus, by the Institute of Peripheral Sciences (ICP).
- Finally, the work of the Wildlife Rangers Club of Suriname (WRCS) focused on youth and environmental protection and biodiversity was presented, whose great challenge is to formalize and obtain a bank account and funds to expand their activities.

Figure 11. Participant presenting group work carried out

5) Fisheries Management Group

- Some Amazonian communities have state-recognized fishing agreements. However, there are still many legal gaps in Peru and Colombia, for example, where fishing regulations are not adapted to the Amazon context.
- This group highlighted many achievements that have been gradually achieved. The premise is that fisheries can be an allied tool for conservation if it is properly managed.
- Some challenges in the management of the pirarucu or paiche (*Arapaima gigas*) were discussed, which vary according to country. For example, challenges in relation to the allocation of fair prices, which is a common challenge with all products associated with the bioeconomy. This is due to the difficulty of communities to obtain adequate value for their products and the very high production chain investments required.
- The importance of the end consumer paying more for fairer and more sustainable fishing chains was highlighted. And in some cases, the imposition of minimum purchase prices is suggested, although in many cases studies on the production costs of various products are still lacking.
- In Ecuador, many fishermen prefer to operate informally, fearing restrictions if they are officially registered.
- In Peru, the need for the already established Community Fisheries Agreements to be respected is emphasized.
- It was noted that fish do not respect political borders, creating challenges in border regions such as smuggling and overfishing, which are difficult to control.
- Finally, the impacts of river gold mining were highlighted, affecting personal safety and food, with high contamination of fish and water. For example, in some Amazonian cities, such as Cobija (Bolivia) or Puerto Maldonado (Peru), the consumption of fish has been discouraged. Recent reports of pollution influence policies against fishing, which would affect artisanal fishing associations, such as the Association of Artisanal Fishermen Río Napo, in Ecuador. It concludes that there is still much to learn about the true magnitude of pollution, as well as strategies to deal with this threat.

Darío Emilio Casimiro:

In fishing, for example, we take care of the resource, but others come from outside and take it without permission. That is very demotivating.

Figure 12. Participant presenting group work carried out

6) Timber and Non-Timber Resources Management Group

- Cases of timber and non-timber resource management in Brazil and Bolivia were discussed, identifying economically relevant Amazonian products with good acceptance in national and international markets.
- Timber and other forest products are often perceived as economic reserves within communities. In addition, forest harvesting activities contribute to the rural family economy and the care of the ecosystem, generating sustainable socioeconomic benefits.
- Local productive organizational and technical capacities are strengthened, allowing communities to collectively access the market through their productive organizations.
- In some cases, collective marks and certifications have been implemented, such as the organic production of Amazonian Brazil nuts, which allow exports with differentiated prices and premiums to invest in social services such as health insurance. The institutionalization of collective brands includes resources to promote environmentally friendly practices.
- Interaction and marketing platforms have also been created to facilitate market strategies and strengthen the network of contacts between producers.
- In Bolivia, recent laws on departmental and integral productive development of the Amazon facilitate access to resources and strengthen Amazonian productive organizations.
- It is important to consider that peasant and Indigenous communities often show distrust towards external organizations due to previous negative experiences.

Table 4 below presents a summary of the main points discussed in each of the six groups, according to the type of management:

Table 4. Summary of what was discussed in the 6 groups, by type of management

Territorial management	Participants pointed to key challenges in territorial management, such as the overlap between protected areas and Indigenous territories, the presence of multiple actors with different levels of decision-making, and the complex logistics needed to ensure inclusive participation. Models of territorial governance were also highlighted, such as the large assemblies organized by the Achuar Nationality of Ecuador, which show community forms of coordination and decision-making on a large scale.
Tourism Management	The Ese Eja community of Infierno in Madre de Dios manages a model of community tourism, in which today they operate their own company, Bawaja Expeditions. Their experience shows how conservation and research are key pillars to secure wildlife, generate knowledge, and strengthen locally managed sustainable tourism.
Wildlife/Game Management	The group identified common challenges in wildlife management, such as encroachment by external actors and legal differences between countries in wildlife management. They highlighted that the management of one umbrella species often benefits others, highlighting the importance of integrated approaches.
Educational Management	The group discussed three educational experiences: 1) fire management and fire education in the Xingu Indigenous Territory, addressing the limited participation of Indigenous youth; 2) academic methodologies to engage ethnic groups in Manaus and decolonize education; and 3) the Suriname Ranger Club, focused on youth and challenges of formalization and financing.
Fisheries Management	Some Amazonian communities manage state-recognized fisheries agreements, highlighting important achievements. Fisheries can be an ally of conservation if they are properly managed. Some challenges were discussed, such as the search for fair prices and the social bioeconomy, informality in Ecuador, the need to respect community agreements in Peru, and cross-border problems such as smuggling and overfishing. In addition, the growing threats of river gold ore were discussed.
Management of timber and non-timber resources	The reality in Brazil and Bolivia was discussed, highlighting Amazonian products with good acceptance in national and international markets. There are efforts where local capacities have been strengthened, collective marks and certifications have been implemented, marketing platforms have been created, and sustainable practices have been promoted.

2.4. Presentation of individual posters

In the following activity, each participant had one hour to prepare their poster individually. Each one develops a specific case of collaborative management and answers the following questions:

- *What is the project approach?*
- *Who are the main actors/partners?*
- *What are the biggest challenges?*
- *What's working and why?*

Figure 13. Preparation of individual posters

Figure 14. Preparation of individual posters

Below are five examples of the posters presented during the workshop:

Title: The fruits of collaborative work in the Amazonian fruit production complex in Pando

Presented by: Marco Antonio - CIPCA (Bolivia)

Process:

1. **Articulation of actors:** actors identified and articulated around potentialities.
2. **Diagnosis:** participatory situation analysis around key information fields.
3. **Departmental Assembly:** actors directly linked to the Amazonian fruit chain.
4. **Constituted platform:** led by the Departmental Autonomous Government of Pando. Social cohesion!
5. **Political advocacy of the platform as a productive complex:** approval of laws.

Actors: small peasant producers and Indigenous Peoples, subnational government, private companies. / **Counterparts:** national government (decentralized entities), cooperation agencies, academia.

Achievements:

- Creation of the Amazonian Productive Development Service for Comprehensive Technical Assistance (SEDEPRO).
- Public-private transfers for small producers.
- Allocation of 5% of the departmental General Treasury of the Nation (TGN) for the promotion of Amazonian fruits. Law 021 of 04/30/23.
- Institutionalization of government programs.
- Designation of origin for products.

Title: The protection of the endangered species of red goldfinch (*Spinus cucullatus*)

Presented by: Angelbert Johnny - South Rupununi Conservation Society (Guyana)

Actors: village councils, forest rangers, the South Rupununi District Council. In addition, the Guyana Wildlife Conservation and Management Commission, the Environmental Protection Agency, the Guyana Land and Cadastral Authority, Smithsonian Global.

	<p>Main challenges: the state refuses to recognize community conservation on state lands; illegal capture; fires; habitat destruction.</p> <p>What is working well and why? Community decisions; communities recognize their own conservation, respecting rules and regulations; monitoring; communities own important areas for birdwatching and tourist attractions; communities signed memorandums of understanding with each other, both with the Southern Rupununi Conservation Society and with the District Council.</p>
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</p>	<p>Presented by: Saira Bucheli - Association of Artisanal Fishermen of the Napo River (Ecuador)</p> <p>Project focus: To maintain sustainability by seeking a balance between production and profits, in order to care for and protect our fisheries resources.</p> <p>Actors: Undersecretary of Fisheries, municipal governments, NGOs, fishermen's associations, illegal fishermen.</p> <p>What is working well and why? The support of WCS, one of the most active actors with the Fishermen's Association, providing workshops and trainings, the use of the ICTIO app and now, Smart ICTIO.</p> <p>Main challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - They did not socialize this information with the Fishermen's Association. - They are leaving many families without economic support and without work. - They do not offer alternatives for fishermen. <p>"YES, TO FISHING" "YES, TO WORK"</p>
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Presented by: Robin Durán - Baawaja Expeditions, Native Community of Infierno (Peru)

Project Focus: Promote ecotourism and research through conservation, creating tours or packages in Tambopata, Madre de Dios.

Actors: The Ese Eja Native Community of Infierno, with the collaboration of NGOs and private organizations.

Main challenges: That the people of the native community adapt to some changes necessary to achieve a more successful project.

What is working well and why?

The good communal organization, the Board of Directors and the Tourism Management Committee.

Presented by: Dario Baniwa - Federation of Indigenous Organizations of the Río Negro (FOIRN)

Project focus: intercultural research in the Río Negro, knowledge for management

Actors: FOIRN and Instituto Socioambiental (ISA)

Main challenges: Recognition: degree/academic. Support in the structuring of the plan to confront and adapt to climate change.

What is working well and why?

- Diversity and Fish Management and Fisheries
- Wildlife Management
- Forest landscape
- Forest management and capoeira management.

Figure 15. Presentation of individual posters

DAY 3: PRACTICES IN ACTION. TOOLS, BEST PRACTICES AND COLLABORATION

The opening of the third day placed the discussions on a more practical and comparative level, recognizing that collaborative management is expressed in very different ways depending on the territorial, political and cultural context. From the outset, it was made explicit that the experiences presented should not be read as models to be replicated mechanically, but as situated processes, shaped by local histories, specific legal frameworks, and particular power relations. On this day, the main challenges to effective collaborative management were discussed, and experiences with a gender perspective, inclusion of young people, and equitable benefits were shared.

Karen Kainer:

Diversity of experiences is not a problem; it's precisely what allows us to learn more honestly.

3.1. Understanding the challenges

Based on the posters prepared the previous day by the participants, a list of external and internal challenges to Indigenous Peoples and local communities that affect collaborative management was started. This list was then completed in plenary by all the participants.

External Challenges:

- Illicit activities.
- Regulations that limit collaboration or solution implementation.
- Market dynamics that affect the sustainability of initiatives.
- Lack of incentives in universities to promote collaboration with local actors during the research process.
- Impacts of climate change.
- Absence of strategies to maintain lasting connections between actors.
- Bureaucracy that delays or complicates the execution of projects.
- Tensions between non-governmental organizations.
- Lack of trust between sectors.
- Short-term projects with high staff turnover.
- External projects not aligned with the "life plans" of the communities.
- Lack of government support to respond to the needs of communities.
- Protected areas in opposition to the interests of the surrounding population.
- Disjointed actors.

External and Internal Challenges:

- Persistence of a colonizing mentality.
- Need to understand problems holistically and value multiple perspectives.
- Difficulty communicating information in an appropriate and accessible way to a wide audience.
- Unequal power relations.
- Long distances make it difficult to access communities.
- Lack of adequate logistics and infrastructure.
- Insufficient resources to consolidate initiatives.
- Shortage of trained personnel.

- Diversity of values and perspectives could generate disagreements.
- Lack of up-to-date or reliable data.
- Distrust between the actors involved.

Deyvis Huamán Mendoza:

One of the most important challenges we have in Peru's protected area system is the perception of the communities residing within protected areas about these areas. We currently have a goal of 50% of the funds for protected areas going to communities and the other half going to conservation itself. In Peru we have a diversity of public funds that are not used.

Internal Challenges (local communities and Indigenous Peoples):

- Internal conflicts.
- Economic dependence on carbon credits.
- Problems related to legislation or land regularization.
- Need to ensure the participation of young people and women - including mothers with children - in collaborative spaces.
- Lack of solid communal organization.
- Absence of technical training in environmental issues within the territory.
- Need to adapt to social, economic and environmental changes.

Figure 16. Plenary work

Saira:

For me, the biggest challenge we are suffering in our productive association is the action of some NGOs. I think it would be appropriate for them to agree, because there are some that help and others that harm. An international NGO, in collaboration with an Australian university, recently launched an article saying that our river fish are being polluted by heavy metals, including mercury, without thinking about the consequences for fishing communities. As a result of these publications, the government of Ecuador wants to prohibit fishing, which would affect many families, whose source of economic income depends on fishing. This prohibition not only affects us as an association, but also the Indigenous Peoples who fish for subsistence. The relationship of trust with this NGO has been broken, because we even support in the collection of data. And other NGOs that are doing a good job are affected, because our association has already broken trust in NGOs in general.

Figure 17. Plenary work

Dario:

Within the context of Río Negro, territorial and geographical extension is already a challenge in itself, because it makes access difficult. I also want to comment on the challenge of funder bureaucracy. These international cooperation projects are not always aligned with the life of the project or of the communities. Additionally, there is an absence of State inspection and monitoring. Also, the lack of project longevity and continuously rotating foci, sometimes conducted in secrecy, leaves the initiative without a lasting permanent strategy. Within the communities we face illegal fishing, drug trafficking, to name a few challenges.

3.2. Sharing success stories in collaborative management

The participants were randomly divided into 6 groups to discuss success stories where collaborative management is managing to overcome some of the challenges mentioned above.

The facilitators clarified that by success we mean processes where something is being worked on in an innovative way, because we understand that the challenges are constant. Emphasis is placed on the actions that workshop participants and their organizations/institutions are currently working on.

The cases presented by each group showed contrasting trajectories. In some territories, co-management emerged from solid community processes; in others, it arose as a response to external conflicts or pressures. These differences made it possible to analyze how the role of the State, the market, and external organizations can strengthen or weaken local processes. Despite these challenges, the experiences showed a high capacity for local innovation, combining traditional knowledge, community agreements, and strategic alliances.

Table 5. Some strategies that respond to specific challenges

Challenge	Successful strategies
Local actors dependent on intermediaries	In the Igarapé Lourdes Indigenous Territory, in Rondônia (Brazil), the creation of the COOPERVEKALA cooperative has made it possible to generate income through activities such as reforestation, rubber production, and the sale of Brazil nuts and cumarú. Thanks to the cooperative, families expanded their access to different market players and began to negotiate directly with intermediaries, even doubling sales prices.
Logistical and economic limitations to present results of research, management, and monitoring to communities that are remote.	<p>Example 1: In Brazil, the organization RedeFauna shared how the use of Google Meets and WhatsApp groups – made possible by the recent connectivity provided by Starlink – has facilitated the dissemination of research results among communities and allies.</p> <p>Example 2: From WCS Ecuador, the "Jaguars Forever" program works to change negative perceptions about the species, since many people focus on domestic animal attacks by jaguar. The program brings together schoolteachers to talk about the natural history of the jaguar and its ecological importance, gauging participant perceptions before and after the workshops. In addition, they evaluate whether these changes are maintained in the long term. They have estimated that, for each teacher trained, learning is replicated in their schools and reaches about 40 more people.</p> <p>Example 3: In Medio Juruá (Brazil), the arrival of Starlink allowed greater connectivity, but also increased the circulation of <i>fake news</i>. A funder temporarily covered the service, but when the support ended, the community returned to using the radio. The Juruá Institute created a network of communicators and an online radio, where news summaries are prepared and then distributed to the communities through loudspeakers.</p>

<p>Initial work on land rights to later promote effective management</p>	<p>In Bolivia, the Center for Research and Promotion of Peasants (CIPCA) has carried out research on public policy and inter-institutional coordination in the context of peasant and Indigenous families, focusing on the processes of conflicting land tenure claims and territorial titling in the northern Amazon of the country. In addition, they have carried out evaluations on the productive and organizational dynamics of the communities.</p> <p>For their part, participants from Brazil pointed out that many communities still do not have official documentation of their lands and that regularization processes are progressing slowly due to FUNAI (Fundação Nacional do Índio) delays.</p>
<p>Conflicts between actors</p>	<p>Example 1: For CIPCA in Bolivia, research is a key element for decision-making and the formulation of public policies. They have mapped the work of various institutions – including NGOs – that contribute to local agendas, aiming to strategically improve, strengthen, and coordinate actions. From this process, the Inter-institutional Platform of Amazonian Fruits of Bolivia (PICFA) was created, a space from which projects are defined in direct collaboration with the communities.</p> <p>Example 2: In Colombia, the Ministry of Environment and Sustainable Development has promoted a governance table for peace and conservation, linked to forest management, land titling, and the construction of agreements, although many of these efforts are not yet documented. Multi-stakeholder meetings have also been organized to define strategies to combat deforestation in the Colombian Amazon. These meetings bring together about 100 people every three months to be held accountable, discuss specific projects, and consolidate a work agenda with local communities.</p> <p>Common conclusion: In both examples, it was clear that active listening and participation from the community base are essential to build legitimate and effective proposals.</p>
<p>Conflicts with external actors utilizing resources without permission</p>	<p>Example 1: In the Middle Juruá region (Brazil), Fisheries Agreements made it possible to regulate resource use and generate a significant increase in pirarucu harvests. This territorial agreement arose following conflicts when external actors harvested community resources and made threats against community members. A forum that convened public actors and included external fishermen (five families) as part of the agreement, expanded the pirarucu monitoring area, registering more than 2,000 fish in just one year, up from 500 the year before. The fisheries agreement stands out as a key tool for conflict mediation and territorial planning. In addition, community associations strengthened the commercialization of pirarucu, allowing better prices and more efficient management of the species, which today is recovering in several areas.</p>

	<p>Example 2: In the Middle Rio Negro (Brazil), fisheries management focused on transforming the highly predatory sport fishing practices of the tucunaré açu (<i>Cichla temensis</i>). Over time, a community-based tourism association was created that structured ethnotourism and ecotourism initiatives with collective benefits, including courses for responsible capture of the tucunaré açu. Community management plans require private companies to participate in regulation, which was only possible thanks to the strengthening of territorial protection by communities.</p>
<p>Reconciling interests of protected areas and those of the surrounding population</p>	<p>Natural protected area systems are increasingly incorporating participatory management approaches. General strategies include training of government officials; sharing information in appropriate spaces with clear agendas and values such as empathy and exchange; mapping actor interests and seeking possible solutions to facilitate collaboration. All this contributes to building a shared vision about the usefulness and purpose of the protected area.</p> <p>The need to promote women’s participation and ensure childcare when organizing workshops was also underlined. It was also discussed that the creation of community conservation areas can be an effective strategy to combine the benefits of conservation and social development, integrating protection of biodiversity with local well-being and income generation. Another key point was the importance of having organizations that act as mediators between communities and the government, a role that sometimes falls to NGOs. In this context, two specific examples were presented:</p> <p>Example 1. The ethnotourism experience within a federally-recognized Indigenous community tourism project (The Pico da Neblina, known as <i>Yaripo</i> by the Yanomami people), located within the Pico da Neblina National Park and the Yanomami Indigenous Land, on the border between Brazil and Venezuela. This unique experience of ethnotourism (versus ecotourism) occurs, in an area where a park and Indigenous lands overlap. This case is recognized as the first formal experience of building a tourism plan with an Indigenous community and highlights a successful example of joint management.</p> <p>Example 2. The Pilon Lajas Biosphere Reserve and Community Land of Origin (RB - TCO) in Bolivia, located between the departments of La Paz and Beni. This territory, recognized for its high biodiversity, is managed in a shared manner with 23 Indigenous communities. The work includes articulation of monitoring tools, life plans, and community management plans, allowing access to funds, training, and other resources for territorial monitoring. In addition, they hold monthly inter-institutional meetings.</p>

	<p>These experiences show a break with a common paradigm in conservation - the idea that protected areas remain protected simply because they exist, in contrast to territorial planning agreements and active management practices as protection mechanisms.</p>
<p>Regulations not appropriate to the Amazonian context</p>	<p>Important work has been carried out on regulatory and institutional reform.</p> <p>Example 1. The construction of a proposal for a legal framework for Amazonian community freshwater fisheries, developed from a "bottom-up" participatory approach in 13 regions of the Peruvian Amazon. This proposal seeks to differentiate itself from national fisheries regulation - mainly focused on marine fishing - and is based on the promotion of fisheries agreements to strengthen collaborative management and to control and surveil the territories.</p> <p>Example 2. The case of CADAP, the Amazonian Council for the Development of Aquaculture and Fisheries in Peru. A national fisheries research agenda has been articulated by a group of government actors linked to Amazonian fishing. This agenda is connected with financing sources and has been structured using a watershed approach, becoming an initiative with great potential. Although the document has not been officially registered and the law has not yet been approved, it continues to serve as a strategic guide for the freshwater fishing sector agenda.</p>
<p>The need to connect Amazonian production with local consumption.</p>	<p>Food and production arrangements and policies that adapt regulations to local production realities were highlighted. An illustrative example from Brazil reveals that some regional food assistance programs distribute imported canned fish, even though local Amazonian fish is available for catch and distribution. Local fish cannot be incorporated into these programs because it does not comply with required health certifications.</p>
<p>Creation of international organizations that effectively represent Indigenous and local communities.</p>	<p>The Global Alliance of Territorial Communities (GATC) (composed of AMAN, AMPB, COICA, APIB and REPALÉAC) is a coalition of Indigenous Peoples and local communities, representing 35 million people in forest territories in Asia, Africa and Latin America. While these regional organizations face similar challenges, until recently, they were not articulated with each other. They recognized, however, the need to come together globally to generate a greater impact.</p> <p>To ensure the functioning of the alliance, representatives were identified within each organization, and external allies – financial, legal and other strategic areas – were brought in to support its collective work.</p>

<p>Intertribal collaboration versus conflict</p>	<p>Intercultural collaboration for the defense of territorial rights. One example comes from the Rio Negro, where two Indigenous groups who had historically been rivals and involved in territorial conflicts - the Aruak and the Tukano - decided to unite. Today they are part of the Federation of Indigenous Organizations of the Río Negro (FOIRN), from where they work together to protect their territories against colonization and external invasion.</p>
<p>Collaboration with private companies</p>	<p>In the Ese Eja Native Community of Infierno, currently made up of 232 families, a 20-year contract was signed in 1996 with the company Rainforest Expeditions. Renewed later for another 20 years, the management of the tourism enterprise was gradually transferred from the company to the Indigenous community. Members of the community were trained as official tour guides, and over time, most of the staff became local.</p> <p>This collaboration also extended to the scientific field, integrating research projects with tourism activity and simultaneously promoting scientific and community tourism within the community.</p>

Robin Durán Torres:

In our community, ecotourism was an option, because we already organized. Without that, it wouldn't have worked.

Katan Jua Tuntiak Patricio:

There are territories where conflict comes first and then management. That totally changes the process.

Some immediate reflections from the thematic leaders:

Galo: The wealth of initiatives and solutions was highlighted, and the importance of territorial rights - a first step to achieve proper management. Other fundamental strategies are to strengthen people's capacities, ensure equitable distribution of benefits, and respect cultural diversity. It is necessary for actors to have clear short-term goals and indicators, since it is very difficult to think about achievements in these challenging socio-environmental contexts without getting discouraged along the way. Galo reinforces the importance of communicating successes and failures to continue internal learnings, strengthen other initiatives, and learn from other organizations.

João: Deliberations revealed that collective action based on diversity, which includes a territorialized science stripped of arrogance, helps to strengthen narratives and propose new horizons for the Amazon and its peoples. He highlights the importance of optimism and hope as essential elements in political advocacy strategies, envisioning a better future without limiting oneself to the challenges of the past and present. That is why this activity was

important, because we talked about strategies that are being implemented that are working. It focuses us on our ability to adapt, because we cannot talk about definitive solutions but rather, processes that work. This exercise of optimism and hope is important for the new generations, to encourage them to continue the good work. It is a strategy of struggle that indicates that there are many solutions that are being carried out from the hands of Amazonians.

Figure 18. Participants during group work

3.3. Experiences with a gender perspective, inclusion of young people, and equitable benefits

This activity focused on sharing understandings of equity, benefit sharing, gender, and youth within collaborative management. From the beginning, it was clear that these issues are not conceived as secondary components, but as structural conditions for the legitimacy and sustainability of territorial processes.

Participants were randomly divided into 6 groups to discuss the following guiding question: *What specific tools, approaches, and practices does your organization use that others here could learn from in the areas of:*

- *gender inclusion,*
- *generational sustainability,*
- *and equitable distribution of benefits?*

There was a strong convergence on the idea that the benefits of co-management are not exclusively economic. They include cultural recognition, organizational strengthening, transmission of intergenerational knowledge, and political autonomy. At the same time, tensions arose regarding how to operationalize equity, especially when efforts and dedicated time between individuals and groups are unequal.

In some groups, the participation of women and young people, the distribution of benefits and the intergenerational continuity of collaborative management processes were addressed in an integrated way. Groups highlighted that inclusion does not happen automatically, but requires internal political decisions, creation of specific spaces, and changes in organizational practices.

It was highlighted that when benefits are concentrated in individuals, conflicts emerge and the collective process is weakened. In contrast, collective benefits strengthen trust, social cohesion, and the sustainability of territorial management. The participation of young people appears to be key to continuity and innovation, although it faces structural limitations.

Below are the specific actions mentioned by groups to address the issues of gender inclusion, generational sustainability, and equitable distribution of benefits.

1) Gender inclusion

Gender inclusion is addressed on multiple fronts, combining institutional, cultural, and everyday practices. Specific actions include:

- Promotion of women's participation in leadership positions, including the presidency of associations.
- Strengthening of the Wapichan Women's Movement in Suriname and other women's associations through projects designed and led by women.
- Recruitment of local staff with a gender perspective and creation of conditions for participation, such as the availability of infant caregivers during meetings.
- Adaptation of gender strategies to each cultural reality, recognizing that the visibility and acceptance of women – and LGBTQIA+ people – varies between territories.
- Compulsory inclusion of women in the boards of associations and promotion of their financial autonomy, for example through the opening of their own bank accounts.
- Consideration of the existing reluctance in some communities and gradual work to transform them. There are differences in the degree of openness towards debates on sexual and gender diversity in community contexts.
- Explicit visibility in the communal statutes of the participation of women, young people, and the elderly.
- Experiences were shared where women accessed their own bank accounts for the first time, breaking the exclusively male management of monetary resources.
- Orientation of European Union budgets towards priority issues for women and young people, such as projects to prevent gender-based violence.
- Capacity-building initiatives at all levels.

Suellen Samanta dos Santos Barreto Baré:

Many times women participate, but we do not decide. Collaborative management has to change that.

2) Generational sustainability

Generational renewal and cultural permanence require specific strategies, including:

- Holding annual meetings to transfer activities and responsibilities to young people and women.

- Incorporation of young people in research processes and creation of spaces such as the Wapichan youth arm in Suriname.
- Progressive transfer of technical and financial responsibilities, accompanied by political training for young leaders.
- Inclusion of young people in production chains and provision of higher education opportunities.
- Generation of mechanisms to include young people without displacing the authority and knowledge of the elderly, such as youth associations and training programs.
- Creation of specialized programs, such as the Fishermen's School, and expansion of access to technology for territorial monitoring.
- Development of technological innovations to better connect with youth. However, caution should be exercised about the role of technology as a tool for youth inclusion versus a factor that promotes individualization.
- Recognition that the distribution of benefits and vitality of the mother tongue varies between territories.
- A reflection was made on the complex impact of religions - mainly evangelical and Catholic - on local cultures and on the intergenerational transmission of knowledge. This impact was simultaneously perceived as modifying social order and as a threat to traditional cultural practices.

Ruth Marilyn Buchapi Velasco (Marisita):

If young people do not feel part of the process, the territory is left without a future.

3) Equitable distribution of benefits

Equity in benefit-sharing requires regulatory clarity and strong collective mechanisms such as:

- Inclusion of young people and women in the distribution of financial benefits from business agreements or transfers.
- Creation of Community emergency funds to cover needs not contemplated by usual funding.
- Community-managed profit-sharing systems.
- Need to go beyond simple quantitative indicators (number of participants) to ones that track participant distribution.
- Provision of specific resources by associations through direct transfers.
- Recognition that equity is complex and requires clear, transparent, and consensual rules. For example, a case of community fisheries management was shared, where for five years some people carried out surveillance without receiving income, and at the time of commercialization, benefits were divided equally. Subsequently, it was recognized that this did not reflect the actual effort, and the system was adjusted to distribute according to days worked.
- Allocation of a fixed percentage of commission to cover basic expenses of an association.
- Valuing cultural knowledge, infrastructure, and capacity building, as well as financial return.
- Need to allocate a part of the income to collective funds to guarantee sustainability and community resilience.

Darío Emilio Casimiro:

The market can help, but it can also destroy if there are no clear rules.

Beyond equitable distribution at the local level, it was highlighted that communities bear much of the cost of protecting large territories, without receiving fair compensation from the market. This situation is aggravated in contexts of state abandonment, precarious infrastructure, and lack of access to differentiated markets. In this sense, the need to include complementary mechanisms, such as payments for environmental services, long-term financing, and fairer production chains, was discussed.

João Campos-Silva:

Communities are sustaining conservation through their own efforts, but that is not sustainable without structural support.

Karen Kainer:

If the market doesn't recognize the value of caring for the territory, we're asking communities to subsidize global conservation.

Discussions on markets revealed divergent positions. For some participants, insertion in differentiated markets represents a key opportunity to strengthen community autonomy. For others, markets continue to be profoundly asymmetrical spaces, which can weaken territorial logics if they are not properly regulated. It was agreed that the bioeconomy can only be considered "fair" when it recognizes the value of territorial care and reduces dependence on intermediaries.

Rodrigo Marcelino:

It is not a question of rejecting the market, but of entering it with more collective strength.

Regarding this activity, the reflections of the thematic leaders were:

Galo: There was a strong agreement between the groups: the issues of equity and inclusion are not optional if legitimate and sustainable co-management is sought. The need to strengthen women's education, guarantee their representativeness in decision-making spaces and, in some cases, use quotas to ensure balanced participation in the directives was discussed. The importance of strengthening the leadership capacities of women and youth was also emphasized, recognizing the knowledge they contribute, including those related to non-timber forest products and medicinal plants.

The need to implement mentoring programs and generate safe spaces where issues such as gender violence can be dealt with was mentioned. Another key point was to ensure direct access to resources, which allows greater economic autonomy. Galo stressed that the elderly have fundamental knowledge for the survival of communities, while young people can contribute with technologies for monitoring and communication.

On benefit-sharing, the importance of having clear and transparent rules was underlined. The benefits are not always economic. They can include percentages of production, access to employment, and collective resources for health, education, and infrastructure. The influence of religion on culture was also discussed - a relevant aspect that often goes unnoticed. In conclusion, equity and inclusion require culturally sensitive design, leadership, and facilitation, as well as monitoring mechanisms that go beyond the participant count and allow for the evaluation of active participation, especially of women and youth.

João: The most effective way to protect the rainforest and biodiversity is through actions led by local peoples. A clear example is the management of the pirarucu, where around 5,000 people protect 15 million hectares day and night. Communities build guard houses, organize rotating rounds, and devote time and effort to constant monitoring of the resource. However, João remarked that all these costs fall on the communities, because the market does not cover the investment necessary to ensure this protection and almost no production chain is economically sustained on its own. The situation is aggravated by centuries of state abandonment, without infrastructure or basic services, which makes it very difficult to develop competitive production chains in the territories.

The market tends to leave the least profits precisely to those who have less political and economic power. Competing with commodities or cheap labor is unfeasible for communities. For this reason, Brazil is discussing the need for direct payments for environmental services that complement what the market pays for and to guarantee decent living conditions for those who protect biodiversity.

We are facing a great cultural challenge. In many territories, there is a strong need to affirm local identity and maintain their culture, especially among women and young people. And although there is a territory and productive activities, young people live with constant global influences through cell phones and look for spaces to develop their subjective opinions. When locally-grounded identity and cultural spaces do not exist, they are often occupied by external actors, such as churches that reach even remote places. This reinforces the urgency of strengthening local cultures, ways of life, and opportunities for expression, especially for youth in Amazonian territories.

DAY 4: COMMITMENTS, PARTNERSHIPS, AND THE ROAD AHEAD

The day begins by summarizing what was done the day before and what will be covered today. First, lessons learned about collaborative management during this workshop are shared by each of the participants. Then, they share in groups, discussing what they think happens when collaboration works and how to make actors feel heard. This was followed by a discussion on how to strengthen intercultural knowledge that promotes collaborative management. Finally, they talk about workshop products that can be of benefit to participants followed by next steps to take as a group.

4.1. Lessons learned from the workshop

The group is divided into pairs to highlight some learnings that participants are going to take home. Participants recognized that many expressed differences are not easily resolved, but that making them explicit is an essential step in moving forward. The need to build common languages was underlined, including promotion of the concept of collaborative management, without erasing the differences between communities, organizations, academia, and the State, was underlined.

Maria Cunha:

We talked about what experiences we take away from these moments in our territory, and I mentioned something that had a great impact on me during these workshop days: the resilience of the people who are here, their willingness to promote the quality of life in the spaces where they work, either within the organizations in which they operate or contributing to improving the quality of life of their communities.

Deyvis Huamán Mendoza:

We were talking about what marked us the most on the first day, and for me it was very impactful to hear how other people define collaborative management. From the State or from NGOs we usually have an idea of how it is articulated or coordinated, but from the point of view of a fishing organization – a group of people or communities that take advantage of a resource – collaborative management is understood as a strength: working together to improve a production chain and, with it, improve quality of life. That has marked me a lot and is one of the most significant lessons from this meeting.

Pahmela Barbosa:

We talked about how to adapt everything we hear here to apply it also in traditional and Indigenous communities living in urban contexts. We reflect on how to replicate the tools and experiences that have worked in conservation units and in more remote communities and take them to communities that today are suffering violence and multiple effects precisely because of the lack of collaborative management. The central question was: how can we implement truly collaborative management within urban communities?

Collaborative **management is based on trust**, co-responsibility, and adaptation to diverse contexts. To represent this, a dynamic activity was performed where participants in pairs took turns doing guided walks where one participant led their partner with their eyes closed across the room and then expressed what they felt. The metaphor of "guided walking" appears as a reflexive axis to understand leadership, mutual care, and different forms of accompaniment in collective processes. It was stressed that collaboration is not uniform: there are multiple valid ways to guide, support, and build together, depending on people, links, and territories.

4.2. Discussions about what makes collaboration work and actors feel heard

Subsequently, group discussions followed where participants are divided into three groups by mother tongues (one in Spanish, one in Portuguese, and one small in English) to discuss the following guiding questions:

- *What have we learned about what makes collaboration work?*
- *What should happen for all parties to feel that their needs are being met?*

The groups then shared their main discussions in plenary, sharing the following main points.

Figure 19. Plenary discussion

1) What have we learned about what makes collaboration work?

- Have a common goal.
- Ensure that actors take ownership of the collaborative space and understand their role.
- True alliances are not built from specific requests, but from the co-definition of objectives, methods, and priorities.
- Have structure and management mechanisms that facilitate collaboration.
- Share common themes, goals, and interests.

- Build trust between NGOs, Indigenous Peoples, local communities, associations, governments, and other relevant actors, even the invisible ones.
- Guarantee equal conditions for participation.
- Practice empathy.
- Have adequate information and knowledge.
- Identify together the problems of the territory and possible solutions.
- The existence of previous territorial and community plans allow communities to evaluate new external proposals from an organized and proactive position. These locally developed plans function as frameworks for deciding which projects to accept, how to implement them, and who should participate.
- Ensure the willingness to collaborate and commitment of all allies.
- Conduct an analysis of the current state and define clear objectives.
- Create a suitable space, with confidence and clear rules.
- To have, when necessary, financing.
- Maintain open, transparent, and constant communication.
- Promote alliances and create bridges between actors.
- Integrate knowledge: traditional, technical, Indigenous, and scientific.
- Work to protect territories.
- Understand and value the perspectives and knowledge systems of others.
- Recognize that collaboration takes time and resources to bring people together.
- Encourage collective decision-making with real commitment.

Galo Zapata-Ríos:

Collaboration does not mean always agreeing, but knowing how to work with disagreement.

2) What should happen so that all parties feel that their needs are being met?

- Flexible commitments that allow you to adapt to changes.
- Constant communication, continuous negotiation, and active listening.
- Knowledge of and respect for current regulations.
- Alignment between incentives and actor needs.
- Ability to interpret and understand different points of view.
- Protection of intellectual rights.
- Recognition of different visions and the balance between conservation and quality of life improvement.
- Clarity on the priorities of each actor.
- Good internal organization and adequate representation of each party.
- Respect for human rights and differentiated priorities.
- Effective participation in decision-making and ensuring that all voices are heard.
- Celebration of achievements to strengthen collective identity.
- Access to concrete benefits: clear rules, financing, recognition.
- Specific incentives (scholarships, leadership promotion, etc.) for local actors to be empowered and trained.
- Actions that respond to the demands and expectations of the actors.
- Protagonism of local actors within the collaborative process.
- Building real social cohesion.
- Return and validation of information to build trust.
- Permanent spaces for dialogue.

- Freely elected representatives.
- Adequate accountability mechanisms, for example, the actors are also overseers of how the project is going.
- Identification of common goals.
- Sector-specific engagement strategies.
- Focused plans for decision-making.
- Relationships based on affection and mutual recognition: these are long-term relationships that manage to generate change.
- Processes built from the start, from the bottom up: bringing the perspective of local communities and their priorities.
- Financial sustainability of co-management. Resources are needed to bring people to meetings, publicize, extend, and monitor results, etc.
- Adaptive management.
- Clear governance and consultation protocols.

Figure 20. Closing group activity

4.3. Strengthening intercultural knowledge that promotes collaborative management

Participants are again divided into groups, this time randomly, to discuss strategies to strengthen intercultural knowledge, which is highly necessary considering that territory management occurs in collaboration between local populations with external actors. And that information is needed to know what actions to execute within collaborative management.

The main reflections of the groups were separated into six different aspects, according to the generation of knowledge:

1. Production and documentation of local knowledge
2. Co-authorship and recognition of intellectual property

3. Integration of local knowledge in public policies
4. Technological platforms and innovations for exchange
5. Capacity building, and
6. Communication for territorial management

The group discussions showed a clear convergence around the critique of Western extractive research practices. It is not enough to collect information. It is necessary to co-construct from the beginning, incorporating local languages, timeframes, and ways of socializing knowledge. The traditional academic model is questioned, and alternatives based on orality, accessible digital tools, and shared authorship are proposed.

In addition, criticisms also arose regarding how to operationalize responsible co-authorship, intellectual property, and the use of data in different institutional contexts. It was recognized that, while some organizations advance in collaborative models of knowledge production, others face legal and academic frameworks that hinder these changes.

Karen Kainer:

To say that knowledge is shared is easy; changing institutional rules is much harder.

Galo Zapata-Ríos:

If we do not recognize local knowledge as knowledge, we continue to reproduce inequalities.

The reflections for each of the six aspects discussed are detailed below:

Production and documentation of local knowledge:

- Prior consent is necessary, but insufficient. Local actors must participate from the beginning, including defining which questions to ask.
- Publish testimonies and experiences. For example, documenting stories, experiences, and memories in written and audiovisual form as a way of preserving local knowledge.
- Recognize oral expression as a valid way of transmitting knowledge.
- Naming of new species by the local communities where the species was found. *While formal biology usually uses morphological traits, communities name plants and animals based on ecology and behavior, which provides a different vision.*
- Show respect for rituals and cultural practices, for example, those that local people use to ask permission before starting data collection activities in the field.
- Return results in local languages. Dissemination of information in native languages expands the reach, especially now with the use of the internet.
- Formally recognize local knowledge. Create specific sections in reports and articles to explicitly acknowledge the contribution of communities, avoiding treating their knowledge as anecdotal or general.

Collaborative and participatory research processes:

- The process by which information is collected is just as important as the final result.
- Differentiate between knowledge generation in the territory and in academia. Both are valid, but they respond to different logics.
- Research based on local interests should be encouraged. Examples:
 - Water quality monitoring ("Is the water I'm drinking clean?").
 - Studies on changes in fish migration patterns.
 - Relationship between fish migration and palm fruiting.
- Participation of decision-makers at the local level in all stages of the research process includes project design, definition of questions, monitoring of success indicators, data analysis. Do not limit the community role to just answering questions or supporting in the field.
- Consult local participants about the final destination of information. If a community decides that certain data should not be published due to cultural sensitivity, that decision must be respected.
- Processes to document useful information for local decision-making, such as participatory mapping of sacred places and ethnomappings of living culture, which allow identification of:
 - Knowledge holders;
 - Where activities are carried out; and
 - When and how they are carried out.

Co-authorship and acknowledgment of intellectual property:

- Include local people as co-authors. There are already examples of scientific articles where associations and communities are co-authors on publications.
- Adhere to external project evaluation processes within the community, whereby leaders consult communities before accepting externally led research or interventions, prioritizing actors with relevant local knowledge
- Recognize local participation, intellectual property, and image rights in a fair way.

Integration of local knowledge into public policies:

- Promote a paradigm shift, which implies recognizing that local knowledge is not simply an "object of study", but situated, and is a valuable forms of knowledge.
- Incorporate local worldviews into regulations and management plans. For example, in Colombia, the Feline Conservation Plan of the Ministry of Environment and Sustainable Development includes Indigenous community recommendations in the action plan. One Indigenous territory recommended maintaining a system of rituals to balance human-feline relations, interpreting the infamous human-wildlife conflicts as signs of spiritual imbalance.
- Adapt technical language to make it accessible, avoiding overly academic terms when social or ecological processes are already understood by communities.

Platforms and technological innovations for knowledge exchange:

- Citizen science for species monitoring. For example, the ICTIO app, where fishermen record the type of species caught and quantities, and data is visualized at individual and regional levels. This is a citizen science tool for the Amazon basin, designed for fishermen

and other actors to record fish observations, helping to understand fish migrations and the state of aquatic ecosystems.

- Local audiovisual production.
- Examples of Amazonian cinema in Peru made by young people trained by recognized filmmakers.
- Documentary that demonstrates paiche handling by the Paumari people. The documentary demonstrates appreciation for how the community distributes roles: fishermen, cooks, and narrators. Here the young people were responsible for the audiovisual recording.
- Real-time exchange of environmental and climate information. Example: alerts on rapidly changing river levels that help to make fishing decisions and support navigation safety.
- Face-to-face or virtual spaces for the exchange of knowledge. While face-to-face is ideal, virtual connections expand the reach of community when mobility is difficult.
- WhatsApp groups for immediate coordination and management, with representatives of various sectors and thematic subgroups. It is useful for quickly systematizing learning and producing guides or manuals.
- Community radios and podcasts that tell life stories can be key tools for sharing deeper intercultural knowledge.

Capacity Building:

- Intercultural undergraduate programs, where students do research in their own communities and give back the results. Example: The intercultural education course at the Federal University of Goiás, where students from the Xingu Indigenous Territory are supported in their local research processes. These efforts are possible if access can be guaranteed through scholarships, which is critical to ensure participation of Indigenous and other local youth.
- The training and empowerment of community interpreters as intercultural bridges. They can use emerging technologies and help create work protocols with external actors.

Knowledge for Territorial Management:

- Recognize the effectiveness of community knowledge and territorial management. Local agreements and knowledge can be as valid and efficient as Western scientific tools.
- Look at each territory without simplifying processes. Avoid reproducing protocols from one community to another, without considering particular local dynamics.
- Promote discussion spaces with an adaptive management approach. Example: South Rupununi Conservation Society (Guyana, Wapichana territory, the only officially recognized Indigenous territory in Guyana). In the past, researchers imposed their questions when studying biological diversity. Now, with the creation of the SRCS, the projects are developed from within the territory, with Indigenous leadership.

After these workshop group activities, the thematic leaders present their reflections on the matter:

João: You pointed out that, even before thinking about products from this workshop, it was essential to define how to build them in a fair and intercultural way. João recalled that at the beginning of his career he produced articles without including local populations, which upon reflection, led him to learn to value co-authorship and the full participation of all actors. He explained that today he seeks to create knowledge together with the communities, incorporating orality and other modes of expression; for example, using WhatsApp audios to write, analyze

and reflect collectively, allowing everyone to contribute their voices and priorities. He also pointed out that the afternoon discussion would focus on strengthening intercultural knowledge in collaborative management and identifying tools for joint construction, even when it is not possible to meet in person, so that the network created is not diluted and serves as a basis for final products.

Galo: Communities need to be involved from the beginning of the processes: defining research questions, planning data collection, and participating in data analysis using methods that make sense to all parties. The objective is that their contribution is recognized in the final products made together. Although there is progress, it is still not enough to obtain free and informed consent. It is necessary to ensure active and continuous participation at every stage.

4.4. Products of this workshop

The closing of the workshop consolidated an appreciation of the workshop as a safe space to express differences and build trust, laying the foundation for future collaborations.

Galo Zapata-Ríos:

We leave here with more questions, but also with more clarity about who to walk with.

As a result of the conversations held over four days, it was agreed to create a WhatsApp group to serve as a space for exchange and follow-up among the participants, with rules of coexistence focused on maintaining the central theme of the workshop: *"Collaborative management focused on Indigenous Peoples and local communities"*. This group will allow the sharing of links, videos, and relevant institutional materials, as well as maintaining contact with each other.

It was announced that the video interviews conducted by the project's communications team will be shared soon. In addition, the biographies and photographs of the participants will be published on the [The Power of Connections website](#).

The organizers of the workshop reported that they will prepare a detailed report and an executive summary to reflect the main learnings from the workshop. Then, an infographic will summarize on one page the main reflections of the workshop. In addition, it was proposed to organize one or more virtual meetings in the coming months to follow up on the agreed collaborations and open new possibilities for connection and shared learnings that arise after participants return to their homes.

Some participants understand that documents to be generated, such as the detailed report and executive summary, to be academic. Thus, they encouraged organizers to also work on practical guidance or protocols as a final product. Karen Kainer reiterates that everyone will be recognized as contributing to the report and that they should feel free to suggest and work on additional products.

Candy and João reinforce the opportunity and importance of making a guide or protocol on the following specific topics that were discussed in the workshop, such as intercultural collaboration on knowledge generation and good practices in relation to women's and youth empowerment.

Karen Kainer:

Collaborative management is a process under construction, and this workshop is just one more step.

4.5. Connecting wheel

During this activity, participants moved freely around the room, interacting with different colleagues to identify common interests, recognize shared experiences, and establish links that could lead to future collaborations. This dynamic consisted of a space for interaction and reflection between peers or small groups, in which quick dialogues enabled participants to understand motivations, areas of work and knowledge of each participant. This exercise made it possible to detect affinities and possible meeting points between people from different backgrounds.

Participants shared some of the topics and details of these new connections:

- Arnold & Robin: Discuss the importance of the Ornamental Fish Tourism Project.
- Rodrigo & Karen: Talked about Amazon nut and being able to share information.
- Rodrigo then spoke with Vanessa about management, institutional strengthening of community bases, and sharing resources and methodologies that their organizations are already implementing.
- Marisa, Maria & José: Discussed the development of community projects and new partnerships with various private actors in the market, as well as the use of communication strategies to disseminate productive activities. They agreed to have monthly meetings to discuss documents and talk about connections.
- João, Candy & Silvia: Talked about starting a practical guide of good practices in collaborative management, based on the systematization of the workshop content. This document would be designed in such a way that it would be readily available and provide an opportunity for all workshop participants to contribute to that document.
- Andre, Robin, Kussugi, Pahmela, Luciano, Silvia, Analu, Érika: They talked about wildlife management. Andre tells a little about the context of that conversation and Kussugi complements by saying that in his community they manage fauna through greater fish consumption. Kussugi then sings a monkey song inviting the men to learn the dance, which is part of the Kuikuro culture.
- Erika invites everyone to join forces to give more voice to the visibility of sacred sites in the context of traditional South American peoples and communities. Then, with members of the government of other countries (Deyvis and Jenny), she mentioned their intent to continue their exchange regarding coexistence agreements in overlapping [protected area and Indigenous territories] areas.
- Candy and Vanessa: Talked about the challenge of organizing life plans in the communities where their NGOs work. They talked about the components of these plans and spaces where financing can be obtained to execute these plans.
- Tuntiak & Dario: Discussed the possibility of co-constructing a proposal - to develop a relationship protocol between FOIRN and Amazon Carbon and work on a deliberate roadmap in Dario's territory, together with his grassroots communities. We have established a possible meeting in the first week of October in which we will take the

opportunity to exchange between my territory and the FOIRN. To facilitate this exchange, I would like to have the products of this meeting.

- Julián, Silvia: Pirarucu exchange / ungulate animal fair.
- Marisa, Silvia: Discussed an exchange regarding extraction of natural oils.
- Robin, Julián & Vane: Talked about the interest of Jurua Institute to promote community tourism, especially as an alternative income in the seasons of low pirarucu fishing activity. They discussed exchanging experiences.
- Jenny with several people: Talked about sharing information to promote public policies for the socio-bioeconomy. She shared more about the integrated plan of 'alternatives to deforestation' from the Ministry of Environment and Sustainable Development of Colombia. She also spoke with Marco about the possibility of exchanging or promoting knowledge dialogues between Colombian and Bolivian communities.
- Robin: He spoke with several people, where he was able to share his community tourism experience and invited everyone to visit their site.

4.5. Lessons learned from this workshop

The multi-day workshop concluded by consolidating collective learning and links between diverse actors in the Amazon. Throughout the process, clear convergences emerged around the centrality of land rights, equity, and inclusion, and the recognition of communities as protagonists of management and conservation. At the same time, persistent tensions related to markets, legal frameworks, scales of action, and internal inequalities were recognized. The cross-sectional comparison of experiences showed that collaborative management does not respond to a single model, but to a set of situated practices that can only be strengthened through continuous dialogue, critical reflection, and collective learning.

The participants' concluding reflections highlighted the human and political value of the meeting. Several people highlighted the opportunity to broaden perspectives, innovate in the way of working with communities, and find a support network that ruptures their feelings of isolation in territorial work. They emphasized the richness of Amazonian interculturality, generosity in exchanging knowledge, and a renewal of energies, hope, and concrete objectives to take back to their communities and organizations of origin. Overall, the workshop not only closed a training process, but also consolidated a network committed to moving towards fairer, more situated, and collaborative forms of Amazonian conservation, understanding the diversity of contexts as a challenge, but also as a fundamental source of strength. Below are some closing reflections from the participants themselves:

- Tuntiak: Having shared with people with diverse knowledge and who are able to open their minds and innovate the way they work with communities.
- Angelbert: Here you can connect with many people. Sometimes you think you're alone in the work you do, but here I realize that I have friends from different countries. This is what I will bring to my community, and I am very proud of this group.
- Luciano: Gaining a bigger perspective of what we do, new solutions, and renewed hope.
- Vanesa: I take from here the opportunity to take a step in the subject I work on and learn from other types of management. I also take with me the generosity to share what we know.
- Jenny: Thank you very much to the organizers of the event and to the other participants for sharing their knowledge.
- José: I gained a lot of contacts, and I hope I can practice the knowledge learned in my community.

- Erika: It has been very enjoyable to have these conversations. This workshop has been a break, meeting people who share the same principles and finding yourself in those conversations.
- Darío: The people who came from other countries in the Amazon, that diversity, has made me feel that we have had a true interculturality of experiences.
- Candy: I really wanted to tell you about what we do in our institution, and that this workshop was not about what you are doing but how you are doing it. For me, this space has been enriching. I take with me what I consider to be an intensive course in Amazonian realities.
- Robin: Thank you to the organizers. This is my first time attending such an event. I am very happy to have been part of this meeting. The experiences of every corner of the Amazon have things in common. I leave with some concrete goals to share with my community.
- Kussugi: I learned a little bit about speaking Spanish. I arrived with the expectation of recharging my energy, and I have achieved that.
- Deyvis: It was very difficult to come, because I had to justify to my office a number of days of my absence, but I leave happy because every day has been worth it. When I am in meetings with managers of protected areas, questions appear to which I did not have answers, but this workshop has brought me answers.

Figure 21. Group of workshop participants

About the project “The Power of Connections”

The "Power of Connections" project is led by the Tropical Conservation and Development Program (TCD) of the Center for Latin American Studies at the University of Florida (UF), in partnership with the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation. "Learning lessons and strengthening coalitions for the conservation of the Amazon" is at the heart of this project, which seeks to connect people and collaboratively develop pathways for the lasting conservation of the Pan-Amazon. This project is funded by the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation through GBMF13270 grants.

About TCD

The mission of the Tropical Conservation and Development Program (TCD) is to connect theory and practice to promote biodiversity conservation, sustainable use of natural resources, and human well-being in the tropics and beyond. TCD is a research and training program of the University of Florida's Center for Latin American Studies, with 10 tenured faculty and approximately 100 affiliated faculty across campus. The program has a long history of collaboration with partner organizations in the Amazon and support networks of conservation professionals committed to sustainable development.

About the Moore Foundation

The Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation promotes scientific discovery, environmental conservation, and the special character of the San Francisco Bay Area. Since 2001, its Andes-Amazon Initiative has helped conserve more than 400 million hectares in the Amazon. By 2031, the initiative aims to ensure that 70% of the Amazon biome (forest cover) and the freshwater ecosystems that support it are under effective management and conservation. Visit Moore.org and follow [@MooreFound](https://twitter.com/MooreFound) for more information.

APPENDIX

A. Complete and detailed workshop agenda

Overall goals:

1. Build community among co-management practitioners.
2. Share lessons learned from innovative co-management initiatives in the Amazon.
3. Strengthen connections between community leaders, public agents and researchers, encouraging long-lasting collaborations.
4. Exchange effective, practical tools and principles for co-management with Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities.
5. Share successful experiences that could be replicated in other territories and locations
6. Outline priority next steps for advancing co-management practice.

Time	Topic	Goals	Activity	Details
Monday night, September 1st – AFTER DINNER				
19:30	After dinner Opening Welcome	Create welcoming environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Formal Welcome 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Opener: Host’s Welcome (Joao/Instituto Jurua – 15 min) ● UF/Moore: Karen – (10 min.) ● Brief contextualization of the collaborative workshop organization process: WCS Ecuador / Galo – (5 min.)
20:00	Introductions	Create welcoming environment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Participants introductions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Name/Location on map (live, work) + What I do? (45 min) ● Participants pair-share then introduce themselves and place post its on Amazonia map
Day 1				
8:00	Project context	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Why workshop? ● Agenda/Objectives/Logistics ● Expectations & Norms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Flipchart presentations ● Objectives and Agenda ● Expectations and Norms (acordo de convivencia) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Project Context & Guiding questions (Karen/Galo/ Joao - 20 min.) ● Workshop objectives, agenda, logistics etc. (10 min.) ● Small groups discuss Expectations and present out (30 min) ● Plenary discussion of Acordo de Convivencia (15) ● <i>Consent to record discussions</i>
9:15	Break			
9:45		Define terms/concepts	What do we mean by co-management?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● By country: Small groups discussion (20 min) ● Plenary report out/discussion (20 min)

10:00	Poster or other prep	Share co-manejo projects	Create posters – or alternative* product - of projects *art, music, storytelling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Present/explain guiding questions for workshop and how they relate to previous discussion • Time for participants to begin making posters based on: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Who are the actors, what are their interests and what is their relationship with each other 2. Guiding question #1. 3. Can work in pairs <p>Note: Help available for those who need it + Example of “turning Galo/Joao’s posers into something simpler”</p>
12:00	Lunch			
13:45			Energizer	
14:00	Poster sharing	Share participant co-management project details; Question #1	Sharing/viewing of posters	<p>½ the group “presents” while the other half circulates. Then switch.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manejo madeira (03)? • Manejo peixe (2) • Manejo territorial (02) • Manejo fauna silvestre (02) • Manejo de fogo (01) • Turismo (01) • Outras experiências? <p>As you look at posters, use a post-it or marker to make a note on at least 2 presentations OR, ANOTHER WAY OF RECORDING, where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • You see a connection with your own work • You would like to know more • You might have something to offer them • You know someone or a resource that might be of use to them
15:15	Break			
15:30	Project sharing	Share participant co-management project details; Question #1	Sharing/viewing of posters cont.	
17:00	Break			

17:15	Power of connections	1 st chance to network	Find 1-2 people to talk to – possible connections	How to capture? What about ball of yarn that connects people on a poster board?
18:15	Break			
19:00	Dinner			
<i>Evening Videos (optional – less than 5 min/video)</i>				
Day 2				
8:30	Opening		Looking back/Looking forward	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opener (30min.) • Brief review of Day I and introduction to Day II agenda
9:00	Small group discussion	Shared set of challenges		<p>Based on yesterday’s presentations and discussions, what are the key challenges to <i>successful co-management of forest and biodiversity resources that is truly centered on Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities and considers? (social, institutional, economic, environmental)?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small group discussion by country • Plenary sharing and discussion
10:30	Break			
11:00	Panel OR Participant-driven dialogue			<p>Participant-driven dialogue – organize thematic groups (timber, fauna, aguaculture) and each group prepare question to the poster about the most interesting points. Work with guiding questions as well. (World Cafe style: Key question at each table?? Maybe too directed?) FACILITATOR IN EACH GROUP & A RECORDER (with a few guiding questions?)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. First in thematic groups (how many/group?) 2. Crossing themes in afternoon session? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When did the co-management begin and why? • <u>How did it begin</u> – the relationships? Who was/is involved and why? • How has it evolved - timeline? • What challenges did you overcome or are you working on <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Internal (relationships) (<i>power relationships – who decides; access vs control?</i>) • External (context – outside pressures, political, social, economic, climactic, etc) (<i>power relationships: access vs control – who decides?</i>)

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What have you learned/done that others here could learn from, specific tools, approaches, practices • In what ways does it ensure both well-being and conservation goals in the Amazon? • Sustainability: How do you work to involve different generations? Consider gender?
12:00	Lunch			
14:00	Panel or PDD cont.		Cont.	“How I built this” panels/interviews continue (1:30h)
15:30	Break			
16:00	Discussion			<p>Based on what we have heard, what concrete tools, best practices, and conditions are needed to ensure that co-management Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities? (60min.) OR... Mixed groups visiting cross-cutting themes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What have you learned/done that others here could learn from, specific tools, approaches, practices • In what ways does it ensure both well-being and conservation goals in the Amazon? • Sustainability: How do you work to involve different generations? Consider gender? • Small group discussions, recording on flipcharts (30min.) • Plenary report out (30min.) <p>PLENARY DISCUSSION - WHAT ARE THE KEY TAKE-AWAYS?</p>
17:15	Power of connections	2 nd chance to network	Find 1-2 people to talk to - possible connections	
18:15	Break			
19:00	Dinner			
CONFRATERNIZACION				
Day 3				
8:30	Opening		Looking back/Looking forward	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opener • Brief review of Day II and introduction to Day III agenda

9:00	Discussion		How have diverse actors – communities, NGOs, governments, researchers – effectively collaborated to strengthen and scale co-management systems that are equitable, sustainable and culturally appropriate?	<p>Small group discussion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What have we learned about what makes collaboration work? • What must happen so that all parties feel that their needs are being met? • How are conflict and disagreement best managed? <p>Plenary report out and discussion</p>
10:30	Break			
11:00				How can this group collaborate looking forward? Facilitated brainstorm and discussion
12:00	Lunch			
13:30	Discussion			<p>Products from this workshop (Joao will bring a paper draft) What should be shared at the February summit? Through other channels/networks/social media? Authorship in publications: What are the lessons learned from the members of this group? Who should get credit and how? Best practices. (Facilitated discussion led by Joao and Galo)</p>
15:30	Break			
16:00		Power of connections (1 HOUR)	Find 1-2 people to talk to - possible connections	
16:30	Evaluation			<p>What are you taking away from this workshop? <u>Formal evaluation: QR code & time to complete survey</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What innovative idea did you bring? • What new idea will you take home and apply? • Who did you connect with? Will you follow up with? <p>Plenary:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • X things you liked about the workshop? • What changes would have made the workshop better for you?

17:00	Wrap-up, conclusions and closure	Facilitated synthesis, Closing circle	Closing and conclusions	Facilitated synthesis, Closing circle Final thoughts/closure
18:30	Dinner (& cachaca!) Yes			